

THE IMPLICATION OF INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES IN WORKING MEMORY CAPACITY ON THE STUDENTS' ENCODING PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate the implications of individual differences in students' working memory capacity on encoding performance. Forty-nine (49) undergraduate Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering students at Visayas State University-Isabel participated in the study. The students were classified as having high, medium, or low working memory capacities (WMCs). The p-values of 0.05 for both the speed and accuracy of each classification were used to determine the significance of the differences. The Pearson correlation test was used to evaluate the relationship between the working memory capacity and the encoding performance of the students. The results revealed that although there were differences in the mean values of the adjusted mean square of error which were 83.80 (speed) and 109.11 (accuracy), the differences were not significant because the derived p-value was greater than the value of the confidence level at 0.05. Students with a low WMC exhibited slower encoding performance and higher output accuracy. Furthermore, no significant differences were seen in the students' encoding ability when categorized as having a high WMC.

Keywords: *Accuracy, ANOVA, Encoding Performance, Operations Span, Working Memory*

INTRODUCTION

Working memory plays a central role in all forms of complex thinking, such as reasoning, problem-solving, language comprehension, and encoding. Working memory is a component of overall memory and is defined as the capacity to simultaneously and actively store and process information (Baddeley, 2012). In this study, we use working memory to refer hypothetical cognitive system responsible for providing information required for ongoing cognitive processes, while working memory capacity (WMC) refers to an individual difference construct reflecting the limited capacity of an individual's working memory.

Several studies have been conducted to determine the effects of working memory capacity on various academic tasks. Studies have shown that working memory capacity affects students' performance in various academic tasks. Researchers have attempted to determine the impact of individual differences in working memory capacity on the performance of students, with or without distractions. Numerous studies have revealed that students who have memory difficulties may have deficits in encoding or typing tasks, storing, consolidating, retrieving, or accessing information. Some studies provide evidence that working memory may have a great effect and be influenced by individual differences in working memory capacity on reading comprehension (Christopher and Shelton, 2017; Foroughi et al, 2016), recall tasks (Kane and Engle, 2003), and reasoning (Grossnickle et al, 2016), but not in arithmetic tasks (Christopher and Shelton, 2017). Others have revealed that most low-WM individuals are more likely to be influenced by auditory distraction, as presented in the environment. However, no study has investigated the effects of individual working memory capacity on encoding or typing tasks.

Previous studies have focused on typing tasks anchored in auditory conditions, such as music or noise (e.g. Bramwell-Dicks et al., 2016). These researchers postulated that the presence of vocals in background music reduces typing performance. Another study revealed that music has a positive effect on task performance, depending on the music preferred by individuals (Young, 2003). In this study, we evaluated the novel hypothesis that individual working memory capacity affects the encoding performance of students during silence.

Gaps associated with working memory capacity make students reluctant to engage in typing or encoding tasks, as they tune in and out of the expected outputs of the undertaking. Within this context, students fail to elaborate on incoming information, thereby negatively affecting their encoding assignments. However, its function in encoding is especially evident, because encoding entails processing sequences of data or symbols that are produced and perceived over time. Working memory plays a critical role in the encoding tasks of a student, as they construct and integrate ideas from a stream of successive words in a text.

Today's highly technological and interactive society calls for students and professionals with a well-established level of competence in information and communication technologies to be utilized by various internal and external stakeholders

of an entity. Encoding information is a cognitive process through which thoughts, ideas, or questions are translated into words. Substantial evidence shows that individual differences in the estimates of working memory capacity reflect differences in how effectively people like students can develop their encoding capabilities (Bengson and Luck, 2017).

Although numerous studies have been conducted to evaluate the various factors affecting the encoding competencies of college students, this undertaking aimed to bridge the gap in extant literature by assessing individual differences in working memory capacity concerning students' encoding performance. Therefore, the present study was conducted.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the implications of individual differences in students' working memory capacity on encoding performance.

Specifically, the research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the implications of individual differences in working memory capacity on encoding performance?
2. Are there significant differences in the encoding performance of students with low, medium, or high working memory?
3. Is there a correlation between working memory capacity and encoding performance?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research method, specifically a descriptive survey. This approach is deemed most appropriate for this study as it describes the events aimed at discovering a causal relationship between WMC and students' encoding performance. Observations were conducted to record and view the subjects' performances under controlled conditions. The respondents of this study were forty-nine (49) Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering students at Visayas State University-Isabel, who had no reported hearing or vision problems that could impair the results of the study. The purposive sampling was used in the study. Twenty (20) male and twenty-nine (29) female respondents underwent the experiments conducted in a computer laboratory setting at a temperature between 22 °C and 24 °C. This temperature was based on research conducted by Sansone (2021), which investigated the effect of classroom temperature on students' performance. This temperature was found to significantly enhance students' academic performance test scores in the classroom. Moreover, a computer set station where the working memory assessments were performed by the respondents and Typing Master software was used to measure the encoding performance of the students in terms of accuracy and speed (words per minute). In addition, modified lag tasks and automated operation spans were used to measure the working memory capacity of the students.

RESULTS

Forty-nine (49) undergraduate BSIE students participated in the study. Among them were twenty (20) males and twenty-nine (29) females with ages ranging from 18 to 22 years, with a standard deviation of 2.23. In the high-WMC group, there were seven (7) males and eight (8) females (mean age=19.87, standard deviation=1.31). In low-WMC having an average age of 21.53 with a standard deviation of 2.65 were eight (8) males and seven (7) females. On average, there were fourteen (14) females and five (5) males with an average age of 21 years and a standard deviation of 2.18.

Table 1
Working Memory Capacity Profile of the students

Classification	Average WM Ratio	Mean Age (years old)	Standard deviation	No. of Male	No. of Female	Total no. of students
High-WMC	0.66	19.87	1.31	7	8	15
Average-WM	0.55	21.00	2.18	5	14	19
Low-WMC	0.39	21.53	2.65	8	7	15
Total	0.54	20.82	2.23	20	29	49

Table 1 shows the classification of students' working memory capacity. The table shows that most of the respondents with high WMC were female and had an average year of age of 19.8, while most of the respondents with low WMC were male and had an average year of age of 21.53.

Table 2
Implications of Individual Differences on Encoding Performance

	Silence	
	Speed (words per minute)	Accuracy (%)
High-WMC	26.07	85.87
Average-WMC	20.79	87.89
Low-WMC	25.13	87.67

As shown in Table 3, although there were differences in the means of each classification of working memory capacity given the value of adjusted mean square of error which was 83.80, the differences were not significant since the derived p-value was greater than the value of the confidence level at 0.05. This means that there were differences in the mean speed (words per minute) and accuracy (%) among low-WMC, average-WMC, and high-WMC students in encoding performance but the obtained result of the sample size does not represent the true difference of the entire population.

Table 3
Analysis of Variance in encoding performance as Influenced by the Working Memory Capacity in terms of speed

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Factor	3	364.0	364.00	121.33	1.45	0.234
Error	94	7877.2	7877.20	83.80		
Total	97	8241.2				

In Table 4, although there was a difference in means of each classification of working memory capacity given the value adjusted mean square of error which was 109.11 and higher compared to the obtained value in terms of speed, the finding revealed that there were no differences on the encoding performance of the students as the p-value calculated was greater than the confidence level, 0.05.

Table 4
Analysis of Variance in Encoding Performance as Influenced by the Working Memory Capacity in Terms of Accuracy

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Factor	2	39.10	39.10	19.55	0.18	0.837
Error	46	5018.90	5018.90	109.11		
Total	48	5058.00				

Table 5
Results of the Pearson Correlation Test on the Relationship Between Working Memory Capacity and Encoding Performance of the Students

	WMCS
Speed	0.033 0.821
Accuracy	0.113 0.440
<i>Cell Contents</i>	
<i>P-Value</i>	

It can be inferred from the results that there was no significant correlation between the working memory capacity and the encoding performance of the students. The individual differences in the students' WMC affected the quality of their encoding performance, as can be traced from the data presented in Table 4.

DISCUSSION

To investigate this relationship between working memory capacity (WMC) and encoding performance in undergraduate BSIE students formed the basis for this study; however, some interesting tendencies were found from these results but no significant correlation was obtained from statistical analysis. Table 1 contains demographic breakdowns that indicate a gender disparity among WMC groups. There are more females in the high-WMC group while in the low-WMC group, there are more males. This is important because some studies like those by (Unsworth & Spillers, 2010) have shown potential gender-related variations in WMC usage.

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) both for speed and accuracy in encoding tasks are presented in Tables 2 and 3. Although there were average differences observed between WMC groups, p-values did not exceed 0.05 in any table. It means that these differences could be accidental and not representative of the population. On the other hand, Table 2 has peculiar descriptive statistics. The high-WMC group had a slightly faster mean speed than their low-WMC counterparts although it lacked statistical significance; which is consistent with authors such as (Schulze & Koelsch, 2012), who propose that increased WMC facilitates faster information processing during encoding. Finally, the finding confirms the lack of a significant correlation between WMC and encoding performance through the Pearson correlation test results. However, these findings showed a comparatively minor number of participants, and as such, they are merely experimental. This finding contradicts some existing research, such as (McNamara & Scott, 2001), which suggests a positive correlation between WMC and memory abilities. And so, more research having more samples between working memory capacity and encoding performance requires more investigation.

Conclusions

Based on their findings, the researchers concluded that students' differences in working memory capacity had an impact on their encoding performance; those with high WMC encoded information faster but with less accuracy. Students with low WMC exhibited slower encoding times but higher output accuracy. Furthermore, no significant differences were seen in the students' encoding ability when categorized as having a high, medium, or low working memory capacity. Furthermore, there was no discernible relationship between the students' encoding performance and their working memory capacity.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that the administration of Visayas State University-Isabel needs to make provisions to enhance the encoding competencies of their students, despite differences in working memory capacity. The development of such skills is imperative if VSU-Isabel wants to improve its graduates' employability against the backdrop of a knowledge-driven society. In the context of the results of the study, the researcher recommends that the proposed

measures and faculty members handling computer subjects formulate strategies to continually monitor and upgrade the encoding abilities of all their students. Furthermore, topics that other researchers may consider in this study include the mediating effects of working memory capacity on students' academic performance and individual differences in working memory capacity and reading comprehension.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study had several ethical considerations. This includes:

Informed consent: Informed consent was obtained from the participants, explaining the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and any potential risks or benefits.

Anonymity and confidentiality: Participants' identities were kept confidential and their names were not used in any reports or publications. In addition, all data were kept secure and confidential.

Respect for participants: The researcher treated the participants with respect and dignity and ensured that their rights were protected. This includes ensuring that participants are not coerced or pressured to participate in the study and that they are free to withdraw at any time.

By addressing these ethical considerations, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted responsibly and respectfully and that the rights and well-being of participants are protected.

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